

Co-design and improved tools: Addressing challenges in decision-making for CAP strategic plans

Oral

Ms. Simone Sterly¹, Mx. Carla Wember²

1. Institute for Rural Development Research, 2. University of Frankfurt

This paper is concerned with challenges that actors face in the CSP design and monitoring process in different EU Member States and throughout the design steps of the strategic plans. The results are based on work in the Horizon project Tools4CAP and are the outcome of the analysis of 12 focus groups reports, a literature review in 18 Member States and a EU level online survey (n=38). The results show that challenges resulting from the current multi-level governance of the CAP and its complexity as well as timing issues are the most common. Coordination between the national and the regional level, lack of transparency concerning decision-making processes or consultation results, as well as hurdles related to the volume and/or complexity of CAP documents and technical problems are among the most mentioned challenges. Based on the results six working groups within the Tools4CAP project worked on co-designing new and improved tools to enable actors in the Member States to create more evidence-based and participatory strategic plans. The paper critically reflects on this process and presents an example of a tool that resulted from the co-design process.